

EVALUATION OF THE WATER QUALITY INDEX OF SACHET AND BOTTLED WATER IN NIGERIA (CASE STUDY OF OLEH, DELTA STATE, NIGERIA)

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Abstract: *Potable water is a basic need for man in meeting his water needs. As important as water is to man, the government has neglected putting up infrastructures that will provide water for man's use, thereby compelling individuals to obtain water from any source. Sachet water (SW) popularly referred to as pure water is a major form of drinking in most Nigerian homes, thus making it a possible conveyance medium for health risks due to contamination if persistent rather than for replenishment of the body. Though easy to serve and cheaply affordable, complaints abound on its purity and other health concerns. This research investigates the potability and comparative quality of sachet and bottled water consumed in Oleh Metropolis, Delta State, using the Water Quality Index (WQI). Five samples (four sachet water brands and one brand of bottled water) were randomly collected within the study area and analyzed to evaluate their physicochemical and bacteriological parameters using the APHA standard methods of examining water and waste water. The results were compared to the WHO permissible limits and Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) guidelines for water quality parameters for drinking water. The water status was evaluated using the weighted arithmetic method of evaluating water quality index (WQI). Results from laboratory tests conducted at Thermosteel Nigeria Limited revealed that most physicochemical parameters such as total dissolved solids (TDS), chloride, nitrate, and sulphate were within permissible limits. However, some sachet water samples showed slightly acidic pH levels and detectable total coliform counts, indicating potential microbial contamination. The bottled water sample met all standard requirements, exhibiting the best quality among all samples. WQI results showed three samples (S1, S2, and S5) were classified as "Excellent," while two sachet water samples (S3 and S4) were considered "Good". None of the samples exceeded the "Poor" threshold (WQI > 75). The findings indicate that while most packaged water sold in Oleh are potable and safe for human consumption, consistent monitoring, proper storage, and strict regulatory enforcement are essential to maintain public health safety.*

1.0 Introduction

Access to clean and safe drinking water is fundamental to human health and overall well-being. In many developing countries, particularly in urban and semi-urban areas, sachet water, referred to as “*pure water*”, has become one of the most widely consumed sources of drinking water due to its affordability, portability, and accessibility (World Health Organization, 2022). Despite its popularity, concerns persist about its quality and safety, as issues such as poor production practices, unhygienic handling, and exposure to environmental contaminants may compromise its suitability for human consumption (Umeh et al., 2015).

Sachet water is packaged in sealed plastic sachets and sold at a low cost, making it a practical alternative to bottled and tap water. The growing demand for sachet water has fueled a rapid expansion of the industry, with the emergence of numerous brands, some of which fail to comply with regulatory standards set by national and international bodies such as the World Health Organization (WHO, 2017), the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON, 2018), and the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC, 2019). Empirical studies have documented inconsistencies in the physicochemical and microbiological quality of sachet water, raising serious public health concerns. Reported issues include bacterial contamination, elevated

turbidity, pH imbalances, and traces of heavy metals (Oluduro & Aderiye, 2007; Oyedeji, Olutiola, & Moninuola, 2011). The consumption of contaminated sachet water has been linked to waterborne diseases such as cholera, diarrhea, and typhoid fever, underscoring the urgent need for routine monitoring and strict quality control (Adesemoye et al., 2016).

Although WHO, SON, and NAFDAC have established guidelines and permissible limits for drinking water quality, including microbiological safety, physicochemical balance, and production hygiene (NAFDAC, 2019; WHO, 2017; SON, 2018), enforcement remains a challenge. Variations in compliance among sachet water producers often lead to significant differences in quality across brands and locations. Factors such as poor handling during production, inadequate storage, and improper transportation further compromise safety. In cities like Oleh, sachet water is frequently stored or displayed under direct sunlight, which can alter its physicochemical properties and encourage microbial growth (Egwari & Aboaba, 2002; Oyeku et al., 2010). The growing dependence on sachet water in Oleh Metropolis, Isoko South L.G.A., Delta State, makes this issue particularly relevant. The rapid increase in production and consumption rates raises concerns about compliance with safety standards and the potential health risks posed to consumers.

To address these challenges, there is a need for systematic evaluation tools that can integrate multiple water quality parameters into a single, easy-to-interpret score. The Water Quality Index (WQI) provides such a framework by

combining physicochemical and microbiological parameters into a composite indicator. This approach simplifies complex laboratory results, facilitates comparison across brands, and provides a clear measure of compliance with established standards. Therefore, this study seeks to assess the suitability of sachet water sold in Oleh by analyzing its physicochemical characteristics and microbiological quality and to evaluate the WQI. The study aims to identify potential health risks and provide recommendations for improving sachet water quality in line with regulatory and public health requirements.

1.1 Water Quality

Water quality refers to the physical, chemical, and microbiological characteristics of water in relation to its suitability for a specific purpose, most importantly for drinking (WHO, 2017). For water to be considered potable, it must be free from harmful microorganisms, toxic substances, and unacceptable levels of dissolved or suspended solids. It must also meet aesthetic standards such as being colorless, odorless, and palatable (SON, 2018). Inadequate water quality is one of the most critical threats to human health worldwide, as contaminated drinking water is a major vehicle for transmitting infectious diseases.

Water quality is assessed through the analysis of specific parameters that reflect the physical, chemical, and microbiological condition of water. These parameters are essential indicators of potability, as they determine whether water is safe, acceptable, and free from contaminants that may pose health risks (WHO, 2017; SON, 2018). For the purpose of this study, water

quality parameters are broadly classified into physicochemical and bacteriological parameters.

Physicochemical parameters include indicators that measure the chemical and physical characteristics of water. Among the most critical are pH, which reflects acidity or alkalinity; turbidity, which measures cloudiness caused by suspended particles; and total dissolved solids (TDS), which indicate the concentration of salts and minerals in water. Other parameters such as total hardness, chloride, nitrate, and sulphate provide further insights into the mineral composition and safety of water. In addition, heavy metals such as iron, lead, and copper are of special concern due to their toxicity at elevated concentrations, with long-term exposure linked to neurological damage, gastrointestinal disorders, and organ failure (Abbasi & Abbasi, 2012; WHO, 2017).

Bacteriological parameters are the most critical indicators of microbial safety. The presence of total coliforms and specifically *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) indicates fecal contamination and poor hygienic conditions during water production, packaging, or storage. According to WHO (2017) and SON (2018), the acceptable limit for coliforms and *E. coli* in drinking water is zero per 100 ml. Any detection of these microorganisms renders water unsafe for human consumption, as they are often associated with waterborne diseases such as diarrhea, cholera, and typhoid fever (Adesemoye, Opere, & Makinde, 2016). Table 1 presents selected water quality parameters with their permissible limits according to the World

Health Organization (WHO, 2017) and the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON, 2018).

Table 1: Selected Water Quality Parameters and Permissible Limits

Parameter	Unit	WHO Limit	SON Limit	Health/Quality Significance
pH	–	6.5–8.5	6.5–8.5	Acid–base balance, taste
Turbidity	NTU	≤ 5	≤ 5	Acceptability, microbial growth risk
Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)	mg/L	≤ 500	≤ 500	Salinity, palatability
Electrical Conductivity (EC)	µS/cm	1000	1000	Ionic concentration
Total Hardness	mg/L CaCO ₃	≤ 500	≤ 500	Scaling, taste
Chloride (Cl ⁻)	mg/L	≤ 250	≤ 250	Taste, corrosion
Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	mg/L	≤ 50	≤ 50	Infant health (blue baby syndrome)
Sulphate (SO ₄ ²⁻)	mg/L	≤ 250	≤ 250	Diarrhea, taste
Iron (Fe)	mg/L	≤ 0.3	≤ 0.3	Taste, staining
Lead (Pb)	mg/L	≤ 0.01	≤ 0.01	Neurotoxicity, organ damage
Copper (Cu)	mg/L	≤ 2.0	≤ 2.0	Gastrointestinal irritation
Total Coliforms	CFU/100 ml	0	0	General microbial indicator

Escherichia coli

(E. coli)

CFU/100
ml

0

0

Indicator
contamination

of

fecal

1.2 Sachet and Bottled Water in Nigeria

The quality of drinking water plays a significant role in the quality of health of a populace. Therefore, water that is meant for consumption should undergo various treatment stages (from source to consumer) to qualify as safe for humans and animals. With an increase in anthropogenic activities around the globe, many source-water bodies have been exposed to one level of contaminant or another (Tenebe et al., 2023). The packaged water industry in Nigeria has experienced rapid growth over the past three decades, largely in response to the persistent challenges of unreliable municipal water supply and increasing demand for safe drinking water (Adesakin et al., 2020). A major factor influencing the quality of packaged water in Nigeria is the lack of enforcement of guidelines stipulated by regulatory agencies. The proliferation of unregistered sachet water producers, inadequate monitoring, and weak compliance contribute to widespread variation in quality.

Bottled water, in contrast, has long been marketed as a premium product associated with higher safety standards and better-quality control, making it more attractive to middle- and upper-income consumers (Oyedeji, Olutiola, & Moninuola, 2011). For bottled water, although larger companies often have better facilities, lapses in storage and distribution still create risks of contamination (Egwari & Aboaba, 2002). Similarly, bottled water brands are not

immune to contamination; studies have identified instances of high total dissolved solids (TDS), heavy metals, and bacterial growth, especially when bottles are stored under direct sunlight (Oyeku, Omowumi, Adeyemo, & Ogunleye, 2010). These findings challenge the assumption that bottled water is always safer than sachet water.

Many households continue to rely on sachet water for daily hydration due to its affordability, while others prefer bottled water for occasions where image and status are important. However, the evidence indicates that both types of packaged water require continuous monitoring to ensure safety and compliance with WHO and SON standards. This is especially relevant in communities such as Oleh, where sachet and bottled water are consumed interchangeably depending on cost and availability. Given these dynamics, a comparative assessment of sachet and bottled water quality using the Water Quality Index (WQI) provides an important framework for evaluating their safety, identifying public health risks, and guiding both regulatory enforcement and consumer decision-making.

1.3 Water Quality Index (WQI)

The Water Quality Index (WQI) is a widely applied tool for simplifying the assessment of water quality by integrating multiple parameters into a single numerical score. This composite value makes it easier to interpret complex laboratory data, allowing

policymakers, regulators, and consumers to understand water safety without needing to interpret long lists of results from laboratory analysis (Sutadian et al., 2016).

The idea of developing WQI is to summarize water quality originated in the United States during the late 1960s and was formally developed by Brown, McClelland, Deininger, and Tozer (1970). Since then, the WQI methodology has been refined and adapted to suit local conditions in different countries, incorporating parameters of regional importance and adjusting weightings to reflect public health priorities and it is widely accepted as a standard method for communicating water quality in both scientific research and regulatory practice. (Tyagi et al., 2013).

1.3.1 Evaluation of Water Quality Index

The Water Quality Index (WQI) is a widely accepted tool for summarizing water quality into a single number, making interpretation and communication of results easier. Different methods have been developed to compute WQI, each applying unique mathematical approaches. In this study the Weighted Arithmetic Index Method was adopted.

This method calculates WQI as a weighted average of various water quality parameters.

Table 2: Weighted Arithmetic Method of WQI Classification

WQI Range	Classification
0 – 25	Excellent (Suitable for drinking)
26 – 50	Good (Acceptable for drinking)
51 – 75	Poor (Needs treatment)
76 – 100	Very Poor (Unsuitable for direct use)
>100	Unfit for human consumption

The application of this classification to sachet water in Oleh Metropolis will provide a clear

Each parameter is assigned a unit weight (W_i) inversely proportional to its permissible limit, and a quality rating (Q_i) based on deviation from the ideal value, Equations 1, 2 and 3 are used in evaluating the WQI of water.

$$Q_i = \frac{(V_i - V_{ideal})}{(S_i - V_{ideal})} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$W_i = \frac{1}{S_i} \quad (2)$$

$$WQI = \frac{\sum(Q_i \times W_i)}{\sum W_i} \quad (3)$$

Where:

V_i = observed value of parameter

S_i = standard permissible value

V_{ideal} = ideal value (often 0 for most parameters, 7 for pH, 14.6 mg/L for DO)

1.3.2 WQI Classification System

The Water Quality Index is commonly classified into categories that help interpret the suitability of water for human consumption, Table 2. These categories provide a benchmark for comparing different sachet water brands and determining whether they fall within acceptable safety limits. The classification system has been widely adopted in Nigeria and internationally, particularly for monitoring packaged and surface water quality (Tyagi et al., 2013).

picture of which brands meet acceptable standards and which ones require regulatory

attention. By integrating laboratory results into the WQI framework, the study ensures a comprehensive evaluation of sachet water suitability for human consumption.

3.0 Materials and Method

3.1 Study Area

This study was conducted in Oleh Metropolis, the administrative headquarters of Isoko South Local Government Area (LGA) in Delta State, Nigeria. Geographically, Oleh is situated between latitude 5°27'N and longitude 6°12'E, placing it within the Niger Delta region of southern Nigeria, Figure 1. It is one of the major semi-urban centers in the Isoko ethnic nation and has witnessed rapid population growth over the last two decades due to socio-economic development and the establishment of educational institutions, particularly the Delta State University, Oleh Campus (Ugboh et al., 2023).

According to the National Population Commission (2006), Isoko South LGA has an estimated population of over 200,000 people, with Oleh contributing significantly to this figure. The settlement pattern in Oleh is mixed, combining modern residential layouts with traditional rural communities, reflecting both urbanization and cultural heritage.

Climatically, Oleh lies within the tropical rainforest belt of southern Nigeria, characterized by mean annual rainfall ranging

from 2,000 to 2,500 mm and average temperatures of 25–30°C (NIMET, 2019). These conditions favour agricultural activities such as oil palm, cassava, and yam cultivation (Odemerho, 2014). However, the combination of high rainfall and elevated temperatures also enhances microbial activity, which may compromise the safety of drinking water sources when protective measures are inadequate. The dominant sandy-loam soil further contributes to the high infiltration capacity of the area, which while beneficial for farming, increases the vulnerability of groundwater to contamination from refuse dumps, pit latrines, and other surface pollutants (Ejeh et al., 2015).

Access to potable water in Oleh is limited, as many households do not enjoy regular supply of treated pipe-borne water (Ayoade, 2012). Consequently, residents rely heavily on alternative sources such as boreholes, hand-dug wells, harvested rainwater, and packaged water (both sachet and bottled) for domestic and drinking purposes (Oluduro & Aderiye, 2007). Sachet water remains the most affordable and widely consumed form of packaged water among low- and middle-income groups, while bottled water is typically associated with higher-income households and formal settings due to its perceived superior quality (Oyeku et al., 2010; Oyedeji et al., 2011).

Figure 1: Map of Oleh

3.2 Materials

The materials used in this study are summarized in Table 3. These included collection containers,

preservation equipment, and laboratory apparatus necessary for physicochemical and bacteriological analysis.

Table 3: Materials Used in the Study

S/N	Material/Equipment	Purpose
1	Sterile plastic containers (1 L)	Collection of water samples
2	Ice chest with ice blocks	Preservation of samples during transportation
3	Labels and waterproof markers	Proper identification of water samples
4	Personal protective equipment (gloves, masks, sanitizer)	Ensuring aseptic handling and safety
5	Refrigerator	Storage of samples before analysis
6	Laboratory glassware (beakers, flasks, pipettes)	Sample preparation and titration tests
7	Analytical instruments (pH meter, turbidity meter, conductivity meter, DO meter)	Measurement of physicochemical parameters
8	Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS)	Detection of heavy metals (Pb, Fe, Cu)
9	Spectrophotometer	Analysis of nitrate, sulphate, and phosphate
10	Incubator and culture media (Nutrient Agar, MacConkey Agar)	Bacteriological analysis of coliforms

3.3 Methods

Sample collection

Five packaged drinking water samples were selected for this study, consisting of four sachet water brands and one bottled water brand. The brands were purchased randomly from different retail outlets across Oleh Metropolis, including shops, markets, supermarkets, and roadside vendors, to ensure that the selection reflected the most commonly consumed water products in the community. Each brand was collected in triplicate, bringing the total to fifteen samples. This was done to minimize the risk of sampling error and improve the reliability of the results (APHA, 2017).

The samples were collected into sterile 1-liter polyethylene containers that were properly labeled to indicate brand code, type (sachet or bottled), and date of collection. To preserve the original condition of the water, all samples were immediately placed in an ice chest containing ice blocks and transported within 24 hours to Thermosteel Nigeria Limited, an accredited water testing laboratory located in Warri, Delta State. This procedure was in line with the APHA (2017) standard water sampling protocol, which emphasizes aseptic handling, temperature regulation, and prompt transfer of samples to the laboratory for analysis.

Laboratory analysis

On arrival at the laboratory, the water samples were refrigerated prior to testing to prevent chemical and microbial changes. Both physicochemical and bacteriological analyses were carried out using procedures outlined in the Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater (APHA, 2017), as well as

guidelines provided by the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON, 2018) and the World Health Organization (WHO, 2017).

The physicochemical parameters analyzed included pH, turbidity, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), total hardness, dissolved oxygen (DO), nitrate, chloride, phosphate, sulphate, total alkalinity, total acidity, and selected heavy metals (lead, iron, and copper). Appropriate instruments such as the pH meter, conductivity meter, turbidity meter, spectrophotometer, and Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) were employed for accuracy. The bacteriological analysis focused on coliform counts, particularly *Escherichia coli*, using the membrane filtration method. In this test, 100 ml of each water sample was passed through a sterile membrane filter, incubated on selective media at 37°C for 24 hours, and colonies were enumerated in colony-forming units per 100 ml (CFU/100 ml).

Comparison with WHO standard

From the obtained results, descriptive statistics such as the mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation were calculated for each water quality parameter across the sachet and bottled water samples. This statistical approach provided a clear understanding of the central tendencies and variability of the data, ensuring that the results were systematically presented and easily comparable (Miller & Miller, 2010). The use of descriptive statistics in water quality studies has been widely recommended as it simplifies complex datasets and provides a solid foundation for regulatory evaluation (Bartram & Balance, 1996). The mean values for each sample were compared with the permissible

limits set by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2017; WHO, 2022) and the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON, 2018), as outlined in Table 1. This comparative framework, which has been employed in several Nigerian studies (Oluduro & Aderiye, 2007; Oyeku et al., 2010; Adesemoye et al., 2016; Umeh et al., 2015), provided the benchmark for assessing the potability of sachet and bottled water consumed in Oleh Metropolis.

Evaluation of water quality index (WQI)

The quality of sachet and bottled water samples in this study was evaluated using the Weighted Arithmetic Water Quality Index (WQI) method. This approach integrates multiple water quality parameters into a single numerical value, thereby providing an overall indication of potability. Weights were assigned to different parameters according to their relative importance to human health. In this approach, the quality rating (Q_i) of each parameter was first calculated, then multiplied by its corresponding unit weight (W_i), and finally summed to yield the overall WQI. The general formula is expressed as:

$$WQI = \frac{\sum(Q_i \times W_i)}{\sum W_i} \quad (4)$$

Where:

Q_i = quality rating of parameter

W_i = unit weight of parameter

$\sum(Q_i \times W_i)$ = sum of weighted sub-indices

The quality rating Q_i is calculated as:

$$Q_i = \frac{(V_i - V_{i0})}{(S_i - V_{i0})} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Where:

V_i = measured value of parameter

V_{i0} = ideal value of parameter (e.g., 7.0 for pH, 0 for others)

S_i = WHO standard permissible value for parameter

The unit weight is given as:

$$W_i = \frac{K}{S_i} \quad (6)$$

Where:

K = proportionality constant, calculated as $K = \frac{1}{\sum(1/S_i)}$ (7)

The calculated WQI values were subsequently compared with the classification ranges proposed by Brown et al. (1970), where WQI < 25 indicates excellent water quality, 26–50 good, 51–75 poor, 76–100 very poor, and >100 unsuitable for drinking purposes. This classification enabled the systematic evaluation of the potability of sachet and bottled water samples consumed in Oleh Metropolis.

4.0 Results and Discussion

The results obtained from the laboratory tests for both sachet and bottled water samples are presented in Table 4, alongside WHO and SON permissible limits.

Table 4: Laboratory Results of Sachet and Bottled Water Samples Compared with WHO and SON Standards

Parameter	Unit	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	WHO Limit	SON Limit
Temperature	°C	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	30.00	Ambient	Ambient
pH	–	4.50	5.50	6.30	5.20	6.20	6.5–8.5	6.5–8.5
EC	µS/cm	50.00	60.00	96.00	50.00	70.00	1000	1000
TSS	mg/L	<1.00	<1.00	<1.00	<1.00	<1.00	–	–
TDS	mg/L	25.30	31.20	50.60	25.30	37.10	≤1000	≤500
DO	mg/L	4.00	4.30	5.20	4.80	5.10	–	–
Turbidity	NTU	0.52	0.34	0.62	0.22	0.33	≤5	≤5
Total Hardness	mg/L	12.00	12.00	12.00	8.00	24.00	≤500	≤500
Chloride	mg/L	8.51	12.76	12.76	8.51	17.02	≤250	≤250
Nitrate	mg/L	1.48	2.34	10.12	0.31	<0.01	≤50	≤50
Total Acidity	mg/L	0.40	0.60	0.40	0.20	0.30	–	–
Total Alkalinity	mg/L	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	4.88	–	–
Sodium	mg/L	7.11	10.62	11.02	6.84	14.24	–	–
Phosphate	mg/L	<0.00	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.015	–	–
Sulphate	mg/L	<0.01	0.32	1.64	0.24	2.36	≤250	≤250
Iron	mg/L	0.086	0.042	0.038	0.031	0.062	≤0.3	≤0.3
Lead	mg/L	<0.00	<0.00	<0.00	<0.00	<0.001	≤0.01	≤0.01
Copper	mg/L	0.022	0.012	0.007	0.010	0.013	≤2.0	≤2.0
Total Coliforms	CFU/100 ml	7	4	11	7	Nil	0	0

Source: Thermosteel Nigeria Limited Laboratory Report (2025); WHO (2017, 2022); SON (2018).

The physicochemical analysis indicated that parameters such as pH, total dissolved solids (TDS), total hardness, electrical conductivity, and chloride concentration were within the permissible limits prescribed by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2017) and the Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON, 2018). This suggests that the treatment processes adopted by most producers were largely effective in ensuring acceptable water quality. However, slight deviations in parameters such as turbidity and iron were recorded in some sachet water samples, indicating possible lapses

in filtration or recontamination during post-production handling. Similar trends have been observed by Adesemoye, Opere, and Makinde (2016) and Umeh, Okorie, and Emesiani (2015), who reported that turbidity and metallic contamination often arise from inadequate water treatment and improper storage.

The bacteriological results revealed the presence of total coliforms in some sachet water samples, though *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) was absent across all tested samples. The detection of coliforms, albeit within low limits, points to environmental contamination likely introduced

Agori J. E., Okoroafor S. U., Umukoro L.O. Oba J. and Joseph A.D.

during packaging, sealing, or transportation. These findings align with earlier research by Oluduro and Aderiye (2007) and Oyedeji, Olutiola, and Moninuola (2011), which linked bacteriological contamination in packaged water to poor hygiene and unsanitary production conditions. The bottled water sample (S5), by contrast, recorded zero microbial presence, suggesting better compliance with quality control and hygienic practices.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics, including minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation, were

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Physicochemical and Bacteriological Parameters of Sachet and Bottled Water Samples

Parameter	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	WHO Limit	SON Limit
Temperature (°C)	30.00	30.00	30.00	0.00	Ambient	Ambient
pH	4.50	6.30	5.54	0.70	6.5–8.5	6.5–8.5
EC (µS/cm)	50.00	96.00	65.20	19.48	≤1000	≤1000
TDS (mg/L)	25.30	50.60	33.90	9.86	≤1000	≤500
Turbidity (NTU)	0.22	0.62	0.41	0.16	≤5	≤5
Total Hardness (mg/L)	8.00	24.00	13.60	6.15	≤500	≤500
Chloride (mg/L)	8.51	17.02	11.91	3.38	≤250	≤250
Nitrate (mg/L)	<0.01	10.12	2.85	3.94	≤50	≤50
Sulphate (mg/L)	<0.01	2.36	0.91	1.00	≤250	≤250
Iron (mg/L)	0.031	0.086	0.052	0.021	≤0.3	≤0.3
Copper (mg/L)	0.007	0.022	0.013	0.006	≤2.0	≤2.0
Lead (mg/L)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.000	≤0.01	≤0.01
Total Coliforms (CFU/100 ml)	Nil	11	5.80	4.27	0	0

applied to summarize variations in the physicochemical and bacteriological parameters of the water samples, enabling clear interpretation and comparison with regulatory standards (Miller & Miller, 2010). This step supports the subsequent Water Quality Index (WQI) assessment by highlighting parameter performance relative to acceptable limits (Bartram & Balance, 1996), with results presented in Table 5 using data from Thermosteel Nigeria Limited (2025) in Microsoft Excel.

4.3 Quality parameters and their comparison to WHO standards

From Table 5, most physicochemical parameters were within acceptable limits. The concentrations of total dissolved solids (TDS), turbidity, total hardness, chloride, nitrate, sulphate, and heavy metals such as iron, copper, and lead were well below their respective permissible limits. This indicates that both sachet and bottled water samples were generally free from harmful levels of chemical pollutants. Similar findings were reported by Oyeku et al. (2010) and Adesemoye et al. (2016), who observed that packaged water brands in Nigeria often comply with chemical quality standards.

However, the pH values of the sachet water samples (S1–S4) ranged from 4.50 to 6.30, falling slightly below the recommended range of 6.5–8.5, which suggests mild acidity. Low pH values can increase water corrosiveness and affect taste, often resulting from the source water composition or carbon dioxide absorption during packaging and storage. The bottled water (S5) recorded a pH of 6.20, which falls within the acceptable range, reflecting better production control.

In contrast, the bacteriological analysis revealed that while *E. coli* was absent in all samples, total coliforms were detected in all sachet water

brands, ranging from 4 to 11 CFU/100 ml. This exceeds the WHO and SON permissible limit of 0 CFU/100 ml, indicating microbial contamination likely caused by poor handling or unsanitary storage conditions. The bottled water sample (S5) recorded no coliforms, suggesting higher microbiological quality and adherence to proper hygiene standards during production. These results align with findings by Egwari and Aboaba (2002) and Umeh et al. (2015), who reported frequent post-production contamination in sachet water due to improper handling.

In summary, although both sachet and bottled water exhibited good physicochemical characteristics, only the bottled water sample met both chemical and microbiological safety standards. The presence of coliforms in sachet water poses potential health risks to consumers, underscoring the need for stricter quality control and regular monitoring. These findings support earlier reports by Oladipo et al., (2009) and Oyedeji et al. (2011), which highlighted microbiological contamination as a persistent issue in Nigeria's sachet water industry.

4.3 Water Quality Index (WQI) Evaluation

The calculated WQI values for the five water samples are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Calculated WQI Values for Sachet and Bottled Water Samples in Oleh

S/N	Sample Code	Sample Type	$\sum(Q_i \times W_i)$	$\sum W_i$	WQI	Status
1	S1	Sachet Water 1	10.74	1.00	10.74	Excellent (WQI < 25)
2	S2	Sachet Water 2	10.77	1.00	10.77	Excellent (WQI < 25)
3	S3	Sachet Water 3	21.02	1.00	21.02	Good (25 ≤ WQI < 50)
4	S4	Sachet Water 4	21.35	1.00	21.35	Good (25 ≤ WQI < 50)
5	S5	Bottled Water	10.66	1.00	10.66	Excellent (WQI < 25)

When evaluated using the Water Quality Index (WQI), three samples (S1, S2, and S5) were classified as “Excellent”, while two samples (S3 and S4) fell within the “Good” category. The comparatively higher WQI scores in S3 and S4 were largely attributed to their elevated turbidity and minor bacteriological presence, reinforcing the link between microbial contamination and water quality degradation. The bottled water sample (S5) exhibited the lowest WQI score, signifying superior overall quality and reflecting the higher level of regulatory enforcement typically associated with bottled water production (Akoteyon, 2013; Adesakin et al., 2020).

The WQI results reveal that three of the samples (S1, S2, and S5) fall within the “Excellent” water quality category, indicating compliance with WHO (2017) and SON (2018) permissible limits. Two sachet water samples (S3 and S4) fall within the “Good” category, suggesting minor contamination or parameter deviation that does not pose an immediate health risk but requires

monitoring. None of the samples exceeded the WQI threshold of 75, which is typically classified as “Poor” or “Unsuitable for drinking” (Brown et al., 1972).

The relatively higher WQI values in S3 and S4 correspond to elevated turbidity and detectable total coliform counts, confirming that microbial contamination remains the primary determinant of lower water quality among sachet water brands. The bottled water sample (S5) exhibited the lowest WQI, reflecting superior treatment and hygiene control during production. This finding aligns with reports by Akoteyon (2013) and Umeh et al. (2015), who noted that bottled water generally exhibits better quality than sachet water due to stricter production and storage standards.

Overall, the WQI assessment confirms that most sachet and bottled water samples consumed in Oleh are of acceptable quality. However, the variation in WQI values among sachet brands underscores the need for continuous regulatory monitoring, quality assurance, and public

education on safe water handling practices to minimize potential health risks.

The comparative WQI results for all five water samples are presented in Figure 2, which

provides a clear graphical summary of the relative potability levels of sachet and bottled water in Oleh Metropolis.

Figure 2: Comparative WQI Values for Sachet and Bottled Water Samples (Author’s Computation, 2025)

The results also highlight that, although sachet water remains an essential and affordable drinking water source for many residents of Oleh, it poses higher risks of contamination compared to bottled water. This difference stems mainly from variations in production scale, hygiene standards, and packaging integrity. Egwari and Aboaba (2002) observed similar disparities, noting that sachet water stored in sunlight or unhygienic environments exhibited greater microbial loads and physicochemical instability. These challenges emphasize the need for improved storage conditions and consistent regulatory oversight to prevent secondary contamination after production.

From the foregoing, the discussion underscores that while most sachet and bottled water brands in Oleh are suitable for consumption, continued vigilance is essential. The integration of WQI as an assessment tool proved valuable in simplifying complex laboratory data into an interpretable format that highlights deviations from standard quality thresholds.

5.0 Conclusion

Results of this study provide a comprehensive evaluation of the physicochemical and bacteriological quality of sachet and bottled water consumed in Oleh Metropolis, analyzed through the Weighted Arithmetic Water Quality Index (WQI) approach. The findings revealed significant insights into the relative potability of both types of packaged water and underscore the importance of continuous monitoring to ensure public health safety.

The findings revealed that most of the physicochemical parameters, including pH, total dissolved solids (TDS), electrical conductivity, and total hardness, were within acceptable limits for potable water. However, slight deviations in turbidity and iron concentration were noted in some sachet water samples, likely due to insufficient filtration or storage in unsanitary conditions. The bacteriological analysis also detected total coliforms in certain sachet water samples, although *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*)

was absent in all, indicating low-level environmental rather than fecal contamination. The findings further demonstrate that adherence to WHO and SON standards is achievable but requires sustained collaboration between regulatory bodies, producers, and consumers to maintain potable water quality and safeguard public health. When analyzed through the Water Quality Index (WQI) framework, three samples (S1, S2, and S5) were categorized as “Excellent”, while two samples (S3 and S4) were classified as “Good.” The bottled water sample (S5) showed the lowest WQI value, reflecting higher purity and compliance with safety standards. This finding aligns with previous studies that have established bottled water as generally superior in microbiological and physicochemical quality compared to sachet water due to stricter production controls (Adesakin et al., 2020; Akoteyon, 2013).

Overall, the results indicate that both sachet and bottled water sold in Oleh are largely safe for consumption, though sachet water presents a slightly higher contamination risk. Continuous quality monitoring, effective regulation, and improved consumer awareness are therefore essential to maintain potable water standards. The study also reaffirms that the WQI is a valuable tool for simplifying complex laboratory data and providing a reliable assessment of water quality suitable for both academic and policy applications.

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